

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Flow cytometric evaluation of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* flower extract for determining its antidiabetic properties in human whole blood

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plant products are generally used as immunomodulatory (stimulatory/suppressive/adjuvant) agents for curing various ailments. These activities could be due to the presence of primary and secondary metabolites as already described in the literature. In the present study, we focused on those proteases isolated from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* against specific protein antigen i.e. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) on human diabetic blood samples using flow cytometry. For these studies, determination of protein (Nanodrop) and protease (spectrophotometer) content from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* using phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 3 to 9). Out of these, the most active protease treated with diabetic human blood samples (n=6; fasting glucose level, >180) using diluted and concentrated form of protease (100 µl) and determined its blood counts in the form of lymphocytes, monocytes and granulocytes count and also analysed its forward and side scatter of the cell. The results showed that acid protease (pH 5) showed enhancement in granulocytes count but sudden decline in monocytes count as compared to control. Similarly, there is enhancement in both forward and side scatter after treating with acid protease of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata*. Overall, flow cytometric results revealed that acid protease (pH 5) from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* showed antidiabetic property in human blood samples.

Keywords: *Caesalpinia pulcherrima*; *Phanera variegata*; Protease; Antidiabetic.

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Ethical approval: All these studies were conducted under IBSC guidelines and approved through Savitribai Phule Pune University, India.

INTRODUCTION

Proteins are one of the vital components for unicellular as well as multicellular organisms and these are generally involved in all cellular functions [1]. Apart from protein production, degradation of proteins is also required to

release amino acids and then interact with another amino acid to form new type of protein [1, 2]. So, degradation of these proteins is due to proteases that perform hydrolysis [3]. Till date, thousands of proteases are already identified through bioinformatics analysis [2-4]. The identification of these proteases (acid, basic and neutral)

are mentioned in the literature which is classified on the basis of pH and its mode of action [4, 5]. Recently, researchers focused on those proteases extracted from various medicinal plants and showed its importance in various cardiovascular and inflammatory diseases [6, 7].

One of the cardiovascular diseases i.e. Diabetes mellitus, complex disorder which is directly affecting the metabolic rate of carbohydrates, proteins including lipids as well. The diagnosis and treatment of this disease prevents complications related to cardiovascular system and decreased the mortality rate [8, 9]. Due to diabetes, long term complications will arise such as kidney failure, blindness, stroke etc. [8]. In this study, we focused on proteases extracted from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* and also determined its immunopharmacological activity in human diabetic blood samples (selection of samples on the basis of glucose level, fasting >180).

Flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* (common name i.e. peacock flower; family *Fabaceae*) are bright orange-yellow petals with elongated dark red stamens. The flowers will appear during summer season when weather is hot. In addition, flowers also showed some immunopharmacological properties i.e. relieve chest infections, bronchitis, asthma, malaria fever etc. [10] whereas flowers of *Phanera variegata* (common name i.e. Kanchan; family *Fabaceae*) are generally pink-white in colour along with five petals. Generally, these flowers will appear in late winter and is generally used as food item in South Asian cuisine. In addition, these flowers also showed various medicinal uses especially for curing various diseases such as asthma, ulcers etc. [11, 12]. In the present study, we focused on various acid protease extracted from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* using phosphate buffered saline (PBS) of different pH values on human diabetic blood samples.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of flowers

Flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* were collected from the outskirts of Vidya Pratishthan's, Baramati, Maharashtra, India. These fresh flowers were macerated in liquid nitrogen (-196°C) to prepare fine powder (using mortar and pestle). For protease estimation, first of all estimate the protein content from flowers powder and then estimate the protease content against specific protein antigen, bovine serum albumin (BSA, 1 mg/ml). All these immunopharmacological studies were carried out at 0-5°C.

Extraction of protein from flowers powder

In this study, flowers powder (2 g) were added in two different flask and then add extraction buffer (i.e. 20 mM Tris HCl) dissolved in PBS of different pH concentration ranging from 3 to 9 (pH was adjusted by 1N NaOH or 1N HCl). Incubate flowers powder along with extraction buffer for 5 minutes at room temperature and then centrifuged (6000 rpm; 10 minutes at 4°C). Supernatant was collected after centrifugation and then add similar volume of ice cold acetone.

Incubate the solution for 10-15 minutes at room temperature and then centrifuged. Collect the pellet and washed with ice cold acetone to remove the pigments including lipids as well [6, 7]. Finally, protein concentration of flowers powder (*Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata*) was determined by using Nano drop method.

Crude protease production and enzyme assay

After getting the protein from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* that are dissolved in different pH values of PBS buffer ranging from 3 to 9. For crude enzyme collection, centrifuging the protein content (10000 rpm at 4°C for 30 minutes) and then estimate its protease content against specific protein antigen i.e. BSA.

Calorimetric assay was performed for protease estimation using BSA as substrate. For these studies, add equal volume of BSA and crude enzyme extract of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* in 50 ml tube. Incubate the solution for 2-3 h at room temperature. After incubation, trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution was added pertaining to stop enzymatic reaction. Centrifuging the samples and supernatant was collected and then add similar volume of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution in comparison with trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution. Incubate it another 20 minutes at room temperature [6, 7]. Thereafter, addition of Folin's reagent (500 µl) and the intensity of blue colour was measured at 700 nm within half an hour using spectrophotometer.

Analytical studies (pH and temperature) of crude protease

For analytical studies, different pH series (3 to 9) of crude enzyme extract was mixed with similar quantity of BSA dissolved in respective PBS buffer. BSA used as standard for these studies. Incubate the solution for 1 h at room temperature. In contrast, different temperatures (0°C, 4°C, 18°C, 45°C and 90°C) were selected pertaining to determine the effect of protease activity of flowers against BSA. Quantity of crude enzyme extract

of flowers and BSA solution dissolved in PBS of respective different pH values. For both these tests, Lowry test was performed and OD was measured at 595 nm using spectrophotometer.

Flow cytometric analysis

For these studies, ethical (i.e. Institutional biological safety committee) guidelines were followed and these studies were approved through Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India. In this study, Infected (diabetic; Type 1) EDTA human whole blood samples (n=5; 100 µl) were collected from Mangal laboratory (Pathology lab, Baramati) was pipetted directly into a tube containing 100 µl of diluted and concentrated protease dissolved in PBS of respective pH and then incubated at carbon dioxide incubator (37°C, 5 % CO₂) for 2 h [8, 9]. Afterwards, red blood cells (RBCs) were lysed using red cell lysis buffer (ammonium chloride, potassium bicarbonate and ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid) and then centrifuged. Pellet taken and washed 2-3 times with PBS of different concentration of pH range

from 3 to 9. After centrifugation, pellet (leucocytes) dissolved in PBS (of different pH range) and studied the lymphocytes, monocytes and granulocytes count and also analysed forward and side scatter using flow cytometry [13, 14].

Statistical analysis

Values are represented in the form of Mean ± standard error. The difference between the control and treated groups of proteases from *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* is determined by one way ANOVA test (Bonferroni multiple comparison test).

RESULTS

Estimation of protein content

The results showed that *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* showed higher range in protein content (pH 3 to 9) as compared to blank which is determined in Nanodrop as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Estimation of protein and protease content using PBS of different pH concentrations.

Name of the plant	Protein(NanoDrop) (mg/ml)							Proteases (UV spectrophotometer) (mg/ml)						
	pH 3	4	5	6	7	8	9	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	2.057	15.345	4.576	14.36	14.280	13.979	12.024	-	0.441	0.585	-	0.112	0.156	-
<i>Phanera variegata</i>	13.928	12.189	11.255	12.11	12.763	7.710	10.006	-	-	0.188	-	0.134	-	-

Table 2. Effect of pH and temperature on crude protease.

Acid protease (pH 3-6)

Flower extract (protease)	Temperature (Mean ± S.E)				
	0°C	4°C	18 °C	45 °C	90 °C
<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	0.341 ± 0.04	0.356 ± 0.06	0.351 ± 0.08	0.349 ± 0.06	0.033 ± 0.010
<i>Phanera variegata</i>	0.598 ± 0.02	0.519 ± 0.08	0.411 ± 0.06	0.304 ± 0.06	0.019 ± 0.004

Neutral protease (pH 7-7.2)

Flower extract (protease)	Temperature (Mean ± S.E)				
	0°C	4°C	18 °C	45 °C	90 °C
<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	0.482 ± 0.08	0.446 ± 0.08	0.432 ± 0.10	0.384 ± 0.18	0.068 ± 0.008
<i>Phanera variegata</i>	0.478 ± 0.14	0.444 ± 0.16	0.382 ± 0.14	0.334 ± 0.14	0.052 ± 0.008

Basic protease (pH 7-7.2)

Flower extract (protease)	Temperature (Mean ± S.E)				
	0°C	4°C	18 °C	45 °C	90 °C
<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	0.568 ± 0.14	0.537 ± 0.13	0.522 ± 0.18	0.294 ± 0.09	0.096 ± 0.012
<i>Phanera variegata</i>	0.521 ± 0.13	0.478 ± 0.08	0.412 ± 0.06	0.386 ± 0.08	0.122 ± 0.014

pH

Flower extract (protease)	pH (Mean ± S.E)				
	pH 3	pH 4-5	pH 6	pH 7-8	pH 9
<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	0.514 ± 0.08	0.488 ± 0.08	0.542 ± 0.06	0.476 ± 0.14	0.398 ± 0.12
<i>Phanera variegata</i>	0.498 ± 0.12	0.514 ± 0.06	0.434 ± 0.08	0.402 ± 0.04	0.356 ± 0.05

*Kinetic studies will be done at different temperatures and pH values.

Figure 1. Effect of acid (pH5) protease extracted from the leaves of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* on lymphocytes, monocytes and granulocytes count in diabetic human whole blood. Lysed human whole blood were cultured with protease of particular pH 5 and then observed its blood count using flow cytometer (FACS Calibur). Concentrated and diluted form of protease 0.585 mg/ml and 0.2925 mg/ml (*Caesalpinia Pulcherrima*) whereas *Phanera variegata* (0.188 mg/ml and 0.94 mg/ml)

a) First graph represents blood counts i.e. R1 - Lymphocytes; R2 - Monocytes and R3 - Granulocytes.

b) Second graph represents total blood counts.

FSC - represents Forward scatter and SSC - Side scatter

Events - 10,000; Software - Cell Quest; Flow Cytometer - FACS Calibur; Company - BD India.

Estimation of crude protease production

The effect of variable concentration of PBS buffer, pH (3 to 9) dissolved in respective protein content extracted from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* for determination of protease content through spectrophotometer as shown in Table 1. The results showed that PBS (pH 5) concentration containing flowers protein of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* attained higher level of protease content as compared to control.

pH and temperature

The effect of pH and temperature on protease concentration at different pH and temperatures as shown in Table 2. The optimum temperature and pH of protease content was found to be active at 37°C and pH (4-5 and 6).

Flow cytometric results

In *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata*, the results showed that the maximum effect (Fig. 1) of acid protease (pH 5) was observed at 0.585 mg/ml and 0.188 mg/ml. The results showed that there is decline in the proportion of monocytes but there is enhancement of granulocytes count as compared to diabetic blood

samples. Similarly, forward and side scatter showed rapidly enhanced after treatment with acid proteases extracted from *Phanera variegata*. Overall, the results showed that these proteases showed significant antidiabetic activity against infected human whole blood.

DISCUSSION

According to the literature, numerous proteases are already identified and demonstrated that these proteases played an important role in various cardiovascular diseases including diabetes [6, 7]. In spite of this, correlation between proteases and cardiovascular diseases is still unknown because of upregulation of protease activity represents a cause or consequence of cardiovascular disorders. In the present study, we focused and target those proteases extracted from the flowers of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* against BSA using acidic PBS buffer, pH 5 on human diabetic blood samples and determined its immunological activity through flow cytometer pertaining to determine its blood counts and observed forward (shape and size) and side scatter (granularity of the cell) counts, which represents novel therapeutic approach for treating or controlling cardiovascular diseases especially diabetes. In this study, proteases are optimally active in the acidic or basic or neutral environment and some of them may not be retained with in the environment and mediate their potent

antidiabetic activity.

Lot of scientists including researchers claimed that medicinal plants possessed antidiabetic property and this activity could arise because of active compound that are present in extract or fraction. Most of the researchers explained the mechanism of medicinal plant extract is almost the same as that of standard drugs and this antidiabetic activity could arise because of antioxidant property of medicinal plants. Some researchers also mentioned that this activity could be due to enhancement of insulin secretion by stimulating beta cell. Unfortunately, exact mechanism is very difficult to understand and explained in proper manner [16-18]. According to literature, medicinal plant products are already rich in phenolic compounds, flavonoids, terpenoids etc. which reduce blood glucose levels. In this study, we focused on type 1 blood samples and treated with variable doses of protease and determined through flow cytometer.

One of the essential instruments used in various immunological studies i.e. flow cytometer which provides qualitative as well as quantitative information about preclinical and clinical studies [15]. In this study, the results revealed that after exposure of these proteases (diluted and concentrated) in human diabetic sample showed the enhancement of granulocytes count and reduction of monocytes count as compared to control. Several immunological studies have already claimed and mentioned that reduction or inhibition of granulocytes count that contributes to the incidence of infections in diabetes cases [6, 7]. In an effort to reduce the burden of cardiovascular disease, granulocytes played an extraordinary role in host inflammatory response against various infections including diabetes. Similar type of results are also observed in case of forward (FSC) and side scatter (SSC) determined through flow cytometry [13], the results displayed that these proteases showed an enhancement in forward (shape and size) and side scatter (granularity of the cell) as compared to control. Overall, the preliminary results showed that acidic proteases from *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata* showed anti-diabetic activity.

CONCLUSION

Immunological finding of these proteases from flower extracts was very interesting with respect to decline in monocytes count and enhancement of granulocytes count including forward as well as side scatter that is observed in human diabetes blood samples after treatment with various acidic proteases from *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and *Phanera variegata*, in which the percentages of blood counts including scatter count return to baseline much faster. In conclusion, *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* and

Phanera variegata, flowers demonstrated potent protease inhibitory activity. Further studies are required pertaining to isolation, characterization and elucidation of structures of these proteases.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

This work was carried out in collaboration between four authors. AG and APS designed the study, wrote the protocol and interpreted the data, anchored the field study, gathered the initial data and performed preliminary data analysis. CRA and SRC managed the literature searches whereas AG and APS produced the initial draft. The final manuscript has been read and approved by all authors.

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